

Interview Questions

What are your thoughts on public reporting in Finland?

1. Is public reporting applicable in Finland considering the healthcare system in Finland?
2. What are the issues that will hinder the application of public reporting in Finland?
3. What type of information will you like to see in public reporting system?
4. Will Finns be interested in a public reporting system?
5. Can public reporting system affect the delivery of healthcare services in Finland?
6. Who will be in charge of public reporting systems in Finland (Government, private, third party (Kela, THL municipality))?
7. How does public reporting affect Sote or Vice Versa?
8. What do you think will be the attitude of healthcare service providers towards public reporting systems?
9. Does Finland need a public reporting system now?
10. How will the public reporting systems influence freedom of choice in Finland?
11. Can public reporting systems reduce waiting times in hospitals?
12. Will public reporting system empower consumers in general since they will have a platform to make informed choices?
13. Are there systems similar to public reporting systems already in the healthcare systems?
14. Are they consumer centric or are they for decision makers and hospital administrators?
15. Which sector is likely to implement public reporting systems (private sector or government)?